

Textbook: Focus on Students' National Identity

Terminological Variability in the Category of Educational Publications

Liudmila A. Borbotko (a), Ekaterina M. Vishnevskaya* (b)

(a) *Moscow City University, 129226, Moscow (Russia), 4-1, 2nd Selskokhoziastvenny Proezd*

(b) *Moscow City University, 129226, Moscow (Russia), 4-1, 2nd Selskokhoziastvenny Proezd*

kate.vishnevsk@ya.ru

Abstract

Nowadays is witnessing new challenges related to the current state of the digital era. The phenomenon of digital consciousness that is the result of digitalization calls for the new objectives and instruments in all spheres of human activity. The latter especially concerns education. Nevertheless, new technological perspectives rely on the expertise that comes in the form of verified and approved teaching and learning tools that are books coming in a variety of types. Variability in terms of naming those manuals is linguistically due to the common processes in terminology as well as methodologically explained by the differences in the set of objectives and goals to hit with the help of this or that manual. Moreover, the diversity of manual types which implies variability of terms used to name them is regulated by such principal factors as official recognition and compliance with the curriculum. Still, various manuals that are characterized by different titles, functional and teaching potential have a structure that is strictly determined and obligatory.

Keywords: term variability, teaching manuals.

© 2021 Liudmila A. Borbotko, Ekaterina M. Vishnevskaya

This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published by Moscow City University and peer-reviewed under responsibility of TSNI-2021 (Textbook: Focus on Students' National Identity)

Introduction

Russia is welcoming innovations and changes in all spheres of social and governmental activity with education being no more exception. It is education and science that most call for transformations due to them urging to form the basis for the reasonable, expedient introduction of innovations as well as to promote the latter to younger generations.

Innovative approach in education correlates with the cultural orientation and the anthropocentric paradigm which presents “a challenge that is due to be met employing a new complex and credible approach which is the case of intercultural education” (Borbotko & Vishnevskaya & Nersesova, 2019). The latter generally implies forming and mastering intercultural competence being the ability to operate in appropriate and effective ways in various situations of multilingual and multicultural nature (Deardorff, 2015). Such ability relies on one’s knowledge, expertise, attitudes, experience and skills. Moreover, it is relevant for teachers to be competitive and ready to implement new intellectual products and skills to boost the educational process (Vikulova, 2018). Still, the latter seeks for tools and kits to aid the practice of mastering all kinds of skills and abilities.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The article attempts to analyze terminological variants employed to name training manuals. Such terms as textbook, handbook, training and resource kit, methodological manual, teaching aid are specified. The purpose of the study is to reveal specific features of mentioned manuals, to examine their potential capacity, the typical elements and components, target audience, and subject matter. The objectives are to specify which competencies the manuals develop and which goal every of the manual type pursue.

Literature review

Postmodern era urges a profound reform of the old education system that relies on the realization “that there is no single method or style of teaching / management for all students and teachers” (Bokova, 2020: 48). Thus, it is the uniqueness of each student calling for specific forms of education that is emphasized due to postmodernism. Such approach is realized through various means mostly of digital nature being products of technological advances. The latter in the form of digital technologies are principal for information and educational environment at schools, universities and even when it concerns distance learning and mixed educational patterns. Digital language learning alongside with teaching with technologies have recently become the focus of many researches and are gaining momentum especially due to mainstream distance learning (Carrier & Damerow & Bailey, 2017; Natoli & Hunt, 2019; Perry 2019; Murray 2020). Thus, there is a variety of digital resources from communities in social networks to distance educational systems and personal websites “that enable teachers to implement their IT-competencies and skills in the cyberspace; to select useful data; to share experience with colleagues as well as to create new electronic products” (Vikulova et al, 2020). Nevertheless, the fundamentals of educational process are still books which are tools that are traditional though still efficient and are not going to be substituted by other

types of resources. Thus, various types of books, literally the terminological variability of naming them makes the principal objective of the research.

The second half of the XX century saw the research in terminology gaining momentum which resulted in terminology maintained as a separate comprehensive scholarly discipline. Many scholars in Russia and other countries around the world have been focusing on terminology issues. The number of studies in terminology that regard the essence of term, its definition, lexical and semantic processes involved, the issues of standardization and regulation, as well as term formation and area terminology is skyrocketing (Hildebrand, 2018; L'Homme, 2020).

In comparison to the words typical for everyday speech terms belong to a particular professional sphere and make a constituent of any professional process. Term is a unit of any natural or artificial language that is represented verbally or take any other strict form (Pashaeva, 2015). The term functioning and being applied is due to the field the latter belongs to evolving. That is why a number of features that describe terms together with their formation, functioning and wide use are determined non-verbally. Term is not that informative if employed separately. It is directed at a complete and detailed description of a concept that is relevant for a certain level of science and technology development.

Despite the term being a strict unit that defines a phenomenon common for a certain scientific area or any other sphere of human activity it still may be polysemic, homonymous or synonymous as other language units are, which is covered in many academic papers (D.N. Shmelev, S.V. Grinev, E.A. Sorokina, V.M. Leychik, etc)

Methodology

Variability is common for all language units including terms being not only linguistic but logical ones as well. Nevertheless, term variability differs from common language patterns. The traditional approach regards variability as a fundamental integral language feature. Still, modern linguistic studies of invariants trigger discussions especially when it comes to content invariants. Invariability is essential to the intellectual value of science (Campbell 2020). On the other hand, terminology sees variability / invariability differently due to the features of the concept *term* as it is.

Variability studies contribute greatly to general scholarly knowledge. Concerning terminology in particular, it is of great theoretical and practical importance. If two language units describe one and the same object, the message of the sentence will not change if one of the units is replaced by another (Ivin & Nikiforov, 1997).

The high level of digitalization in the society along with the growing number of information sources available, publications, dictionaries and encyclopedic resources triggers the problem of term unification being of primary concern as even the concept term has more than forty definitions. The most relevant

unification principle is the one of terms being monosemantic. Terminology employs several methods of working with terms. They are as follows: *standardization, harmonization, definition*. If to remember that term is a cognitive tool, it appears obvious that terminology lapses turn into methodological mistakes. Unification proves an effective and widespread way to eliminate excessive diversity by reducing the number of acceptable elements and solutions, bringing them to uniformity. Presently there are certain principles regulating the unification of terms: 1) the term administers the concept, dominates the latter, specifies it and distinguishes from the related areas; 2) term polysemy appears disadvantageous as it triggers confusion; 3) synonymy may also come unfavorable; 4) term is to be unique and clear; 5) finally, a term does not only belong to the lexical system of language but also to the system of concepts within the framework of a particular science, that is, the term is specialized within a specific scientific discipline (Vinogradov & Platonov, 1999). It's frequently impossible to give a clear answer to whether an ambiguous word is an example of polysemy or homonymy – which illustrates the fact that there are no sharp dividing lines in language (Kortmann, 2020).

Today's level of linguodidactics and its basic disciplines (pedagogy, psychology, psycholinguistics, language studies, social and cultural studies) see new terms emerge while the common ones are evolving (the definition supplemented or expanded). Moreover, there are dictionaries that define methodological terms and concepts according to generally accepted categories.

Nevertheless, language teaching being a constituent in relation to pedagogical science urges to unify the existing principles of selecting major concepts as well as to define them.

Results

The specific terminology dictionary created in Samara state social and pedagogical university (Glossary) features the following classification of the terms under study:

- applied learning literature: training materials that are applied in concordance with the curriculum maintained; in turn,
- learning resources: textbook; handbook; lecture course; lecture notes;
- training and methodological resources: teaching aid; reader; workbook; foreign language texts reader;
- educational and methodological literature: training and resource kit; methodological support; teaching guide; a series of teaching materials;
- academic literature: conference book of abstracts; conference proceedings; collection of research papers; monograph; dissertation abstract;
- reference books: dictionary; directory; reference; checklist.

Let us focus on the definitions of the terms under study. Thus, that will drive us to advising their specific features.

To start with, *textbook* is a collection of methodological and training resources that corresponds to the basic knowledge level acquired if sticking to the didactic principles implemented in the State Educational Standard. The latter is the pillar governing the curriculum: the issues to tackle and their sequencing while studying. The contents of a textbook is to characterize the ways of gaining and implementing knowledge in this or that sphere as well as methodological grounds and principles that determine the basic laws and regularities of the field of activity functioning and developing together with the key issues to deal with and the trends to follow. The volume cannot be less than five printed sheets.

Textbooks are created specifically for each level of education and type of educational institutions, as well as for self-education, meeting the goals and objectives of training and educating a certain age and social group. It contains samples of oral and written speech, language and country-specific material. The material in the textbook is structured and come in certain fragments that make up the content of individual lessons or units. Each unit is prone to include a text that is the base for the following exercises, cultural and linguistic commentary to the text, lexical and grammar material accompanied with the drills and some illustrations. The defining characteristic of textbook that helps it stand out among all other teaching resources is the full compliance with the state curriculum and its official recognition. The abovementioned factors traditionally guarantee the leading role of textbook in comparison with handbook, teaching aid etc.

Handbook represents a collection of methodological and training resources that may partially substitute or supplement the corresponding textbook and is officially registered. It is usually aimed at extending the contents of the textbook and may sometimes correlate only with one or several units studied. Still, it is possible to give some distance from the educational programme and from the textbook content if it ensures a more sophisticated approach to topics. It includes up-to-date relevant materials as in comparison with the textbook it takes less time to issue due to more practical and less fundamental nature. Moreover, it may touch upon controversial issues prompting a fruitful dialogue of teachers and students. The volume cannot be less than five printed sheets.

Another option is *training and resource kit* which is added to the collection of methodological and training resources and contains both theoretical information on the academic discipline (or its section), and materials on the methodology of its self-study and mastering. The volume cannot be less than five printed sheets.

One of the primary objectives of this kind of manuals that differs it from textbook or handbook is that it comes in handy while considering distant education when students mostly work on their own. In this case recommendations for the preparation, organization, control, management and boosting students' learning

activities are of paramount importance. The latter, anyway, can also be of use for a teacher when applied in class.

When speaking of training and resource kits we cannot but mention manuals commonly called *teacher's books*, that focus on major issues of methodology, describes the system of conducting educational process, dwells on approaches or methods (system of techniques) of training. The target audience here is a teacher, thus the manual seeks to offer help in fulfilling mundane challenges: how to accomplish the curriculum, how to be rational while studying theoretical material, how to get a better command of the latter and to employ it in practical communicative tasks, how to work with references and how to test students' knowledge.

Finally, *teaching aid* is a collection of training resources aimed at forming and advancing practical skills. It teaches ways of implementing certain theoretical concepts in practice. In some cases, there are laboratory studies, case studies and project works included. It aims at mastering cognitive forms and methods that belong to a certain area of knowledge. Teaching aids accumulate practical tasks that contribute to theoretical material acquisition. Anyway, apart from its practical approach teaching aid can be supplemented with some theoretical aspects (for instance, description of the physical phenomena). The volume cannot be less than six printed sheets.

Let us again emphasize that textbook appears the principal learning tool fully compliant with the curriculum and educational standard, while handbook, training and resource kit, teaching aid are supplementary teaching materials that cover only a few topics as well as represent different views on the material, and seek to achieve specific goals. In other words, handbook urges to supply some extra resources while training and resource kit – to promote independent studies and teaching aid – to master the material under study through fulfilling practical tasks.

Thus, we are to point out the leading role of textbook among all the learning tools. The approach to textbook as the main component of education can be considered generally accepted, as it is due to manage the educational process being the carrier of education content at one and the same time. Prominent scholars including Inessa L. Bim, Olga V. Afanasyeva and Oleg A. Radchenko claim that textbook should make a system that reflects and models the way the key components of the educational system interrelate "in accordance with the living conditions and the level of development of science" (the components being the objectives, contents, methods and means of teaching) (Bim & Afanasyeva & Radchenko, 1999). Trends in modern higher professional education, the introduction of a competence-based approach along with other factors, have promoted new research in this area. The issue gaining momentum is evident according to recent studies (S.G. Ter-Minasova, E.A. Uspenskaya, I.N. Stolyarova, etc.). The transition to a two-level system of higher professional education finds the issue of textbook as a primary learning tool supplemented with other training kits more acute than ever. The new features of the Russian educational

system together with objects and areas of the graduate's professional activity – either bachelor's or master's – prompt us to take a new look at both the content of the textbook and its technological component – methods, approaches, ways of presenting the material, and boosting students' activity (Tareva & Kazantseva 2011).

Nevertheless, textbook is not the only type of university educational tools that attract the attention of researchers. Handbooks also make the object of study (A.P. Minyar-Beloruicheva, T.I. Berezikova). Still, there is some ambiguity in differentiating a textbook and a handbook. In its turn, textbook is integrated with other educational tools and takes a variety of forms and variants. Tamara I. Berezikova, conducted the study of bibliographic and pedagogical sources that revealed the particular feature of higher school textbook in its urge to obtain the following: fundamental knowledge of the discipline, the systematic presentation of educational material, the predominance of conceptual and factual information. On the contrary, a handbook aims at expanding, supplementing, concretizing the material presented in the textbook, providing in-depth study of the discipline, exemplifying factual data against the predominance of specific and methodological information (Berezikova, 2017). There are general requirements for these types of university educational resources and there is evidence suggesting the ability of the textbook in certain conditions to fully model the educational process within the discipline, to manage the use of auxiliary learning tools (dictionaries, videos, texts). Alla P. Minyar-Beloruicheva also highlights the supplementary function of the handbook along with its contents being dominated by the one of the textbooks. Still, she takes into account the possibility of handbook applied instead of textbook regarding the key topics of the new curriculum (Minyar-Beloruicheva, 2010). The constantly changing modern environment sees such qualities of handbook as its "rapidity" and topicality that makes the latter so common among other publication types. There are the following trends in the development of the higher school handbook: personal orientation, focus on practical tasks, interdisciplinary nature, the use of information and communication technologies, modularity and orientation at the autonomy of the educational process.

Current trends in higher professional training prompt the requirements for a modern foreign language textbook being regularly reviewed. The basic principles of its organization are as follows: the principle of competence formation, continuity; the principle of scientific approach to content selection; accessibility; the principle of visibility; students' consciousness and involvement; the principle of studying in cooperation (applying the project method, working in pairs and groups, turning to role-play); autonomy and modularity, which allow to implement the principle of non-linearity of studying. The latter in its turn is rather typical of a modern textbook due to the non-linear nature of the educational process, but applied only to a multimedia textbook. Another requirement for university textbook and handbook is multicompetence orientation as the ability of a training tool to contribute to a comprehensive formation of

competencies of different levels within the same discipline. Today witnesses the requirements applied to the textbook also covering handbooks the latter being of particular relevance.

Speaking about training and resource kits, we emphasize the methodological component, as well as the organization of educational material that encourages independent learning. Let us focus on the teaching aid as a type of manual that allows to meet the needs of the educational process when teaching a foreign language even more quickly. The key feature of the teaching aid is the latter representing the system of practical tasks and exercises for individual and / or group work that focuses on the formation of skills and mastering competencies which does not exclude the presence of theoretical material and involves the use of information technologies. The system of tasks is recommended to include the ones of different levels of complexity from drills to projects that imply creative and research skills.

It appears promising to create teaching aids as modules of a training manual or a textbook with the functions and characteristics inherent in the latter which may contribute to designing a teaching resources constructor. Such constructor implementation demands formulating specific criteria based on certain grounds. It can include already tested materials, ready-made modules that are relevant for working in a particular university. The major advantage of such a constructor is that it contributes to improving the quality of education and the availability of various materials for students and teachers. Thus, it is actually the need for constant updating of educational materials in accordance with the needs of the educational process that forces us to clarify the place and role of the teaching aid in the conditions of non-linearity and individualization of learning and to come to create a new form of the latter.

Having studied the types of books being the basic teaching resources in the varieties of their specific features let us focus on the ones that are common for all the above-mentioned types. Firstly, it is the fact that the volume with no dependence on the number of printed sheets is determined by the curriculum and the number of lessons on the timetable taking into account the framework of the course, its place in the curriculum and its contribution to the training of a specialist.

Another common aspect is the blurb that reads the relevance of the book, what is new to the author (the author's personal contribution) concerning the research, to whom the manual is addressed.

The model of the book includes several obligatory elements though the structure may vary. They are the following:

1. Table of contents;
2. Foreword;
3. Introduction;
4. Main body;
5. Conclusion.

Let us consider each of them in more detail.

Foreword that goes right after the table of contents may have different addressers. Thus, there are “Author’s Note”, “Editor’s Note”, “Drafter’s Note” etc. The primary feature of the foreword is its relatively small volume. Nevertheless, it is to regard the following issues:

1. The purpose of the book (to accompany a theoretical course, for practical or laboratory classes, for the preparation of theses or term papers, for students’ self-study); compliance with the curriculum and the key objectives of the course);
2. The addressee (the year, when the course is read; the specialty for which the manual is intended and the form of training);
3. The kind of the training manual and its correlation with other manuals (within the training package) – if it is a textbook, a handbook, a monograph etc., what the main differences from previously released training manuals of a similar nature are – novelty and comprehensiveness of the training materials, specific features of the author’s concept, of the book structure etc.;
4. Tips on the use of the manual, e.g. the order of units to be tackled, the access to certain elements of the reference block;
5. General features and rules that ensure the efficiency of the training manual. Some of them are the following: the structure of the manual (didactic, reference, bibliographic blocks etc.), the features of indexes, applications, etc.;
6. Author’s personal data is obligatory in case a team of authors was engaged in work on the manual as well as when the book contains several parts.
7. Contact and promoting details – regarding the options for ordering, contacts etc.

Introduction as a structural element represents a text preceding the main body. This is an element of the reference kit.

It is to regard:

- the formulation of the problem covered in the main part of the manual;
- the leading topic specified;
- methods for considering the main topic of the manual justified;
- overview of the current state of the issue under study according to the sources available;
- relevance, problematic and debatable nature of the issue under study;
- presentation of the most important, difficult, and promising topics covered in the main part.

Concerning the *main body* of the book the aspect of primary importance is its clear structure, thus, division into chapters and paragraphs (sections) is to be provided.

On the whole, the main body represents a verbal educational material didactically and methodically processed and systematized by the author.

The text seeks to meet the following basic formal requirements:

- compliance with the curriculum;
- accuracy and reliability of the data provided;
- clarity of the material presentation;
- information accessibility;
- conciseness;
- logic and coherence;
- systemic and continuous nature of the material presented;
- clear structure;
- the text corresponding with the literary language norms.

The text in the main body can be supplemented by following extra items:

- tables;
- pictures and drawings;
- contractions and abbreviations;
- URL;
- footnotes;
- epigraph;
- keywords;
- other constituents.

Another obligatory part of any teaching manual is the one including *reference material* (tables, algorithms, tasks for self-study and self-testing, topics of reports, term papers and theses, a system of exercises, a comprehensive list of mandatory and supplementary reference literature, etc.).

It is advisable to provide test questions and tasks at the end of the main body of the manual.

There is evidence that it is actually self-testing in the form of questions to answer and tasks to tackle that distinguishes educational manuals from other genres and helps the student not only check if the material is comprehended but also to highlight the most important aspects for themselves.

Finally, there comes *conclusion*. The major (general) requirement for the conclusion is that it aims at generalizing the educational material, making principal conclusions, giving recommendations and forecasting future prospects of the research.

It features the following aspects:

- 1) summary of the data presented in the main body, the key findings and trends in the development of the discipline;
- 2) a brief description of the issues unsolved or still challenging;
- 3) recommendations for further study of the academic discipline, including the reading list;
- 4) forecast of the discipline future evolvement;

5) a definite finishing touch.

Let us now consider the examples of educational manuals concerning their typical features. The empirical evidence is represented by books that belong to different categories to verify the results obtained.

Table 1. Categories and structure of teaching manuals.

Category	Author	Name	Correspondence to the programme	Structure	Recommended by
textbook	edited by O.A. Suleimanova	English Communication Perspectives	full (major subject)	abstract – contents – introduction – main body – appendix – disc	Ministry of Education
textbook	N.K. Garbovsky	Theory of Translation	full (major subject)	epigraph – introduction – main body – literature – contents	Union of Translators of Russia
handbook	I.V. Zubanova	Taking Notes in Consecutive Interpretation	full (optional course)	contents – introduction – main body – keys – literature	not specified
handbook	V.N. Komissarov	Contemporary Translation Studies	full (optional course)	contents – foreword – introduction – main body – glossary – literature	Ministry of Education
training and resource kit	E.S. Abaeva	Language Studies in Schemes	partial	introduction – literature – contents	University
training and resource kit	T.S. Makarova	A.Christie "Why didn't they ask Evans?"	partial	main body	University
methodological manual	N.V. Miklyaeva K.M. Revenkova N.U. Shmatko	Linguistic train – English Language Teaching in the Kindergarten and at home	partial	abstract – main body – literature – contents	University
methodological manual	E.S. Nechaeva	Social Stratification of Modern British Pronunciation	partial	introduction – main body	not specified
teaching aid	M.G. Kajtandzian E.I.	Teaching Aid for "Phonetic Choir" course	partial	introduction – main body	not specified

	Dmitrieva				
teaching aid	E.M. Vishnevskaya	Phonetic glossary for "Health Feeling Great" textbook	partial	introduction – main body	University

Thorough study of the abovementioned manuals representing various types of books used in the training process we have come to the following conclusions.

Firstly, it goes as an obligation for the manual to be approved by some of the authorities. The higher the status of the manual (a textbook vs a teaching aid), the more high-level acclaim it is to receive: e.g. the textbook "English Communication Perspectives" is recommended by the Ministry of Education due to its compliance with the Federal Educational Standard and curriculum along with it being aimed at training would-be linguists. On the contrary, there is no data concerning the teaching aid "Social Stratification of Modern British Pronunciation" being recognized as a manual being strongly recommended or mandatory for certain specializations. The latter is due to its supporting nature and its urge to supplement the elective course.

Regarding the functional potential of the manuals they correlate with the general rule of the core programme element and the supporting ones. The textbook is the major and basic one aimed at the consistent mastering of communication skills within the framework of professionally-oriented interaction. In its turn, a teaching and resource kit (e.g. "A. Christie 'Why didn't they ask Evans?") demonstrates a tool that boosts a particular skill - oral speech, for instance.

Finally, the structure proves literally universal and claims all types of manuals to stick to it.

Discussions

The specific features of the books being learning tools must ensure the latter will preserve their place within the educational process, literally forming the baseline for teachers and their students to rely on. To prove the universal truth that future belongs to technological breakthroughs that dominate the dynamic lifestyle teachers tend to design and stick to a new format of work that implies both updated training tools and resources to help students meet the demands of the digital society and boost their competitiveness along with traditional methods that have already provided efficient solutions and are by all means fruitful. The latter methods are mainly due to manuals of various types that ensure the training process runs smoothly and successfully. Variability in terms to name the types of teaching manuals employed aims at distinguishing the primary objectives and goals to hit as well as the roles and functions to be realized. To

avoid confusion, it proves relevant to understand the applicability of each manual and its potential either to be the basic teaching and learning instrument or to serve as a supplement directed at mastering some certain aspects.

Conclusion

To sum up let us once again emphasize the features that are relevant to distinguish the kinds of teaching manuals though each kind complies with a certain structure that is quite universal. Thus, it is the textbook that is to a greater extent, characterized by full compliance with the curriculum, is considered the basic training means, meets the state educational standard, and also contains methodological data in terms of describing the procedure for completing the tasks. Handbooks, training and resource kits and teaching aids while corresponding to a certain part of the curriculum are considered as supporting tools, as modern and flexible information resources that may contain different views on the issues under study. Moreover, training and resource kits to a greater extent emphasize the methodology of the training process, thus they are targeted not only at students but also at teachers along with being a self-study tool. In its turn, teaching aids are essential for drilling and consolidating the training through specifically developed systems of exercises. The abovementioned claims textbook is a basic and indispensable learning tool while teaching aids and training and resource kits are designed to complement it, as well as serve to consolidate and revise the materials already studied.

References

- Berezikova T. I. (2017) Uchebniy tekst vnivuzovskoy literaturi: problemi kachestva [Training Text within University Literature: Quality Issues]. *Mir nauki, kultury, obrazovaniya [The World of Science, Culture, Education]*, 6(67), 232-234.
- Bim I. L., & Afanasyeva O. V., & Radchenko O.A. (1999) K probleme otsenivaniya sovremennogo uchebnika inostrannogo yazika [To the Issue of Modern Foreign Language Textbook Assessment]. *Inostrannie yaziki v shkole [Foreign Languages at School]*. 6, 13-17.
- Bokova T. N., & Milovannova L. A. (2020) Linguo-Creative Thinking in the Context of Dialogue of Cultures in the Postmodern Era. *Proceedings of the Dialogue of Cultures – Culture of Dialogue: from Conflicting to Understanding. European Proceedings of Social and Behavioural Series*, Vol. 95, 47–53.

- Borbotko L. A., & Vishnevskaya E. M., & Nersesova E. V. (2019) Intercultural Education on the Way to Cross-Cultural Prospects. *EDULEARN19 Proceedings*, 4348-4352.
- Campbell, N. R. (2020) *Foundations of Science*. Salzwasser Verlag, 576.
- Carrier, M., & Damerow, & R.M., & Bailey K.M. (2017) *Digital Language Learning and Teaching: Research, Theory, and Practice*. Taylor & Francis, 264.
- Deardorff K.D. (2015) A 21st imperative: integrating intercultural competence in tuning. *Tuning Journal for Higher Education. University of Deusto*. Vol. 3, 1, 137-147.
- Grinev-Grinevich, S. V., & Sorokina E. A. (2015) Polisemiya v obshcheupotrebitelnoy i v spetsjalnoy leksike [Polysemy in Common and Special Vocabulary]. *Vestnik Moskovskogo gorodskogo pedagogicheskogo universiteta. Seriya: Lingvistika [Bulletin of the Moscow City Pedagogical University. Series: Linguistics]*, 4, 51-64.
- Hildebrand N. J. (2018) *Industry 4.0. Terminology, Effects on certain Industries and Consequences for Society*. GRIN Verlag, 103.
- Ivin, A. A., & Nikiforov A. L. (1997) *Slovar po logike [Dictionary on Logics]*. M.: Gumanitarniy izdatelskiy tsentr Vladost [Humanitarian Publishing Center Vladost], 384.
- Kortmann B. (2020) *English Linguistics: Essentials*. Springer Nature, 295.
- L'Homme M. C. (2020) *Lexical Semantics for Terminology: An introduction*. John Benjamins Publishing Company, 263.
- Minyar-Beloruicheva A.P. (2010) K voprosu o printsipah sozdaniya professionalno orientirovannogo uchebnika po anglijskomu yaziku [To the Issue of Professionally Oriented English Language Textbook Design] *Problemi teorii i metodiki prepodavaniya filologicheskikh distsiplin [The Issues of Theory and Methods of Philological Subjects Teaching]*, M.: MSPPU, 93–102.
- Murray J. (2020) *Distance Learning*. ABDO Publishing Company, 24.
- Natoli, B., & Hunt, S. (2019) *Teaching Classics with Technology*. Bloomsbury Publishing, 264.

- Pashaeva, G. B. (2015) Osnovnie printsipi i meri unifikatsii terminov [Main Guidelines and Measures of Terms Unification]. *Gumanitarnie nauchnie issledovaniya [Humanitarian Scientific Research]*, 4-1(44), 65-70.
- Perry, P. J. (2019) *Technology Tips for Ensemble Teachers*. Oxford University Press, 256.
- Slovar spetsialnih terminov [Glossary]. Retrieved 15 January, 2021 from <https://www.pgsga.ru/research/publishing/details/glossary.php>
- Tareva E. G., & Kazantseva E. M. (2011) Deyatelnostno-kompetentnostniy podkhod k sozdaniyu uchebnikh posobiy dlya podgotovki bakalavrov [Activity-Competence Approach to Handbooks for Undergraduate Students Design]. *Vestnik Moskovskogo gorodskogo pedagogicheskogo universiteta. Seriya: filologiya. Teoriya yazyka. Yazykovoe obrazovanie [Bulletin of the Moscow City Pedagogical University. Series: Philology. Language theory. Language education]*. 2(8), 65-77.
- Vikulova L (2018) Features of iSpring suite learning platform for teaching foreign languages. *Espacios* 39 (20): 5. ISSN: 0798 1015
- Vikulova L. G., & Khoutyz I., & Makarova I. V., & Gerasimova S. A., & Borbotko L. A. (2020) Information Resources for Foreign Language Teachers' Self-development: Overview. *Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, IEEEHGIP*, Vol 131. Springer, 119-127.
- Vinogradov S. I., & Platonova O. V. etc. (1999) *Kultura russkoy rechi [Russian Speech Culture]*. M.: Izdatelskaya gruppa NORMA-INFRA M [Publishing Group NORMA-INFRA M], 560.